

Kinetics of the Reaction Between Bromacetate and Thiosulphate Ions at Great Dilutions.

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In a previous communication by one of us (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 45) the results of a study of the kinetics of the reaction between bromacetate and thiosulphate ions in very dilute solutions were presented. It was found there that the variation of the kinetic activity factor with ionic strength in the region 0.0025μ — 0.012μ was quantitatively in accordance with the predictions of the Brönsted-Debye theory. Nine months after the publication of the above paper, La Mer published his work on the same reaction (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 3341, and correction, 1929, **51**, 3678) and his

results indicate that $\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}$ observed is only threefourths of what

is predicted by the Brönsted-Debye theory. The discrepancy between these two sets of results is very great in view of the fact that very accurate results could be obtained in the kinetic measurements of the reaction. The importance of the subject and the far-reaching effects of the general application of the Brönsted-Debye theory are such that we thought it necessary to revise and extend the previous work on this reaction. In this communication we are presenting data obtained over a wide range of temperatures (30° — 90° .)

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental procedure adopted was the same as in our previous investigation (*loc. cit.*).

The sodium bromacetate was prepared as follows:—Kahlbaum's bromacetic acid dried over phosphorus pentoxide was dissolved in pure dry ether so as to make a concentrated solution. To this was added a drop of phenolphthalein solution and then an almost saturated solution of sodium ethoxide in absolute alcohol drop by drop, the mixture being well stirred, until the liquid turned faint pink. Most of the sodium salt formed appeared as precipitate. Next, the mixture was treated with a drop or two of the acid solution to just decolourise the indicator and the precipitate filtered rapidly under a suction and washed with dry ether. The salt thus obtained

was next dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and reprecipitated by the addition of ether. A considerable amount of the salt was thus obtained. It was next filtered, washed with dry ether and the adherent ether was removed by evaporation in vacuum. The salt was preserved in a dish over fused calcium chloride in a desiccator. The purity of the salt was tested by the estimation of bromine in a definite amount of the salt.

Solutions of different concentrations were prepared by weighing out exact quantities of the salt. All the solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

The reaction was followed by adding to known volumes of the reaction mixture, definite amounts of a standard centinormal solution of iodine and titrating the excess of iodine against centinormal thiosulphate.

While working at temperatures above 50°, solutions of sodium bromacetate of different concentrations were kept alongside the reaction mixtures for the same periods of time as the latter to find out if any side reaction (the replacement of bromine in the bromacetate ion by hydroxyl by interaction with water) took place. It was found in all cases that no such action had taken place in the solutions at the concentrations covered by the investigations in this paper.

Table I contains a summary of the results at different temperatures. The figures included in brackets under 30°, 40° and 50° are velocity constants obtained in our previous investigation. It will be observed that the agreement between the two sets of results is quite close.

TABLE I.
0.434 K.

μ	30°	40°	50°
0.00125	—	—	—
0.00250	0.1940 (0.1960)	0.4420 (0.4400)	0.9750 (0.0986)
0.0050	0.2153 (0.2140)	0.4950 (0.4980)	1.080 (1.150)
0.0070	0.2307 (0.2300)	0.5224 (0.5230)	1.156 (1.213)
0.0085	0.2410 (0.244)	0.5460 (0.5400)	1.210 (1.260)
0.0100	0.2510 (0.256)	0.5690 (0.577)	1.260 (1.320)
0.0140	0.2680 (0.275)	0.6630 (0.6610)	1.436 (1.480)
0.0200	0.3040 (0.310)	0.6900 (0.6780)	1.577 (1.600)

TABLE I—(contd.)

0°434 K.				
μ	60°	70°	80°	90°
0·00125	1·860	3·759	7·050	12·90
0·00251	2·050	4·060	7·595	14·10
0·0050	2·290	4·544	8·560	15·67
0·0070	2·440	4·876	9·030	16·99
0·0085	2·540	5·140	9·440	17·86
0·0100	2·650	5·290	9·910	18·50
0·0140	3·078	6·095	11·400	21·14
0·0300	3·328	6·590	12·320	22·85

Discussion of Results.

Log K plotted against $\sqrt{\mu}$ gives straight lines in all cases over the region $\sqrt{\mu}=0\cdot03537$ to $\sqrt{\mu}=0\cdot11$ (for the region $0\cdot00125\mu-0\cdot012\mu$) for data at all temperatures. The slopes of the curves $\left(\frac{d \log k}{d \sqrt{\mu}}\right)$ obtained from these curves are compared in Table II with the slopes calculated from the standpoint of Debye-Hückel theory at different temperatures.

TABLE II.

Temperature	30°	40°	50°	60°	70°	80°	90°
Slope (found)	2·16	2·20	2·23	2·28	2·29	2·29	2·30
Slope (calc.)	2·07	2·12	2·18	2·23	2·29	2·31	2·36

The agreement between the two sets of values is as good as can be expected from the nature of the work.

It can, therefore, be definitely stated that in aqueous solutions for the ions involved in this reaction, the variation of the kinetic activity factor with ionic strength in the region $0\cdot00125\mu-0\cdot012\mu$ is in good agreement with the predictions of the Brønsted-Debye theory over a wide range of temperatures up to 90°.

Temperature coefficient of the reaction rate.—The temperature coefficient of the reaction rate, throughout the temperature range examined, has been found to be practically independent of ionic strength. Table III gives the average temperature coefficient at different temperature limits.

TABLE III-

$\frac{K_{46}^{\circ}}{K_{30}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{50}^{\circ}}{K_{40}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{60}^{\circ}}{K_{50}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{70}^{\circ}}{K_{60}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{80}^{\circ}}{K_{70}^{\circ}}$	$\frac{K_{90}^{\circ}}{K_{80}^{\circ}}$
2.280	2.205	2.102	1.999	1.87	1.85

These values for temperature coefficients lead to an average value of 15680 calories for the energy of activation of the two reacting ions.

Summary.

A detailed study of the kinetics of the reaction between bromacetate and thiosulphate ions in the presence of sodium ions has been made over the temperature range 30°-90° in the region of ionic strengths 0.00125 μ -0.02 μ in aqueous solutions.

At all temperatures, the variation of the kinetic activity factor with ionic strength in the region 0.00125 μ -0.012 μ for the ions involved in this reaction has been found to be in good agreement with the predictions of the Brönsted-Debye theory.

The energy of activation of the two reacting ions has been found to be 15680 calories, from the temperature coefficient of the reaction rates at different temperatures.